

Tourists' on Marine Sport Tourism Attraction, Travel Experiences and Perceived Values

Hsiao-Ming Chang, and Jui-Liang Hsu

Abstract—The purpose of this study is to analyze the cognitive and travel experience the situation of the tourist attraction of the sport tourism in Penghu. This study used a questionnaires, the main island of Taiwan to Penghu in the way of marine sports tourists adopted the designated convenience sampling method, a total of 1447 valid questionnaires. After statistical analysis, this study found that: 1. Tourists to Penghu sports tourism attraction cognitive as "good air quality, suitable for water activities". 2. Tourists in Penghu's tourism experience, "Let me taste the delicious specialties and snacks". 3. The attraction of the sport tourism, travel experience and perceived value are correlated, and both the perceived value with a high degree of predictive ability. Based on the findings of this study not only for Penghu's tourism industry with the unit in charge of the proposed operating and suggestions for future research to other researchers.

Keywords—Sport tourism, travel experience, perceived value, sport attraction.

I. INTRODUCTION

SPORT tourism is defined for the purpose of personal travel for leisure or competition, leaving the primary residence to participate in sports, watching sports games, or travel to visit the sports attractions [1]. Hall defines sport tourism as: "the purpose of your non-business reasons, to participate in or watch the activities of the movement to leave their own range [2]. Standeven and De Knop define the sports department of tourism to non-commercial or business / commercial reasons must leave home or work place travel during this period of active and passive involvement in sports activities may be involved in is incidental to or participate in sports in an organized manner to type [3]. Gibston pointed out that sport tourism can be defined as leisure-based tourism; it allows people to temporarily leave their home range to engage in, watch the activities of the body, or visit the sports attractions [4]. Sport tourism participation type is divided into three types of people travel to participate in sports (movable sports tourism), and watch sports game will be (game will sport tourism) [2] [3]; there is also a visit to the famous sports attractions, monuments, memorials, etc. (nostalgia sport tourism) [4]. Gibson reviewing the research found that people

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who engage in sports and travel for the game, relatively tourists in the holiday time engaged in sports entertainment, activities or watch the game [4]. Whether it is engaged in an activity, or watch a sports event, the movement as "leisure travel" to provide a strong incentive [3], sports participation can provide a meaningful and purposeful "travel experience" [4]. In addition, the exercise can stimulate the tourist resort development and investment [5], contribute to the development of the region [6]. So from the above-mentioned scholars mentioned above, can be learned that the development of sport tourism on the economic front, or have a significant positive impact for the tourism industry and regional development.

Surrounded by the sea in Taiwan, has abundant marine resources, and very suitable for the development of the sea area-based recreational sports. Penghu is Taiwan's largest outlying island, and has abundant natural resources, including natural resources (marine ecology, flora and fauna, sandy beaches, intertidal belt, outlying islands, unique geological land type), humanities resources (historical cultural monuments), etc., to provide tourism development an important foundation. Penghu has abundant marine resources, however, the number of tourists has decreased year by year, the Penghu area tourism operators in the peak season for tourism operators, the majority of the Department of Water Sports-based activities related to sports such as snorkeling, windsurfing, water motorcycles, high-altitude towed umbrella, and so on.

For Penghu's tourism, so visitors to Penghu as a tourism destination, the attractiveness of tourist attractions is necessary. View of the overall business in the tourist areas, tourism resources must be attractive enough to encourage tourists to visit and are satisfied. The tourist area must have the basic features include: attractive focus, service, transportation, information, promotion [7]. Gunn and Var pointed out that the attractive (attraction) constitute the driving force behind the tourism system. Tourism market is a passenger action "driving force", the tourism attraction provides the main "pull". Tourism attractiveness provides two main functions, first induced these attractive and attracts tourist interest [7]. For most people, they will depend on whether these tourist spots them attractive; for example, business travelers and trade center, conference center or factory "pull" to them; The second is to provide the satisfaction of the tourists, this reward (satisfaction) from the tourism - that is a real tourism product at the same time, the tourism industry about development new tourism marketing methods [4], including sport tourism (sport tourism) of promoting the sport tourism scholars believe that the tourism industry one of the important core industries[8]. Tourism

attraction and tourism resources are inseparable; sports tourism attraction is sport tourism resources. Turco, Riley, and Swart point of view of tourism resources explain the types of sport tourism resources, the resources are divided into four, respectively [8]: a natural tourism resources: rock, climate, geology, water, plants, animals; human tourism resources: history / culture, hospitality facilities, sports / recreational facilities, events, and experience; Human sightseeing Resources: the ability to organize activities, human services, around cultural patterns; local communities: tourism potential, be regarded as material resources, and market proximity, fame, the factors can be developed. Sport tourism attraction force is the destination for tourists to watch or engage in the sport about things. attraction may be natural (parks, mountains, wild animals and plants) or artificial (museums, stadiums, shops) in the core of the field of sport tourism is to visit contribute to and respected by sports heroes: the latest sports equipment or unique sports facilities such as stadiums, athletic venues, the stadium arena; renowned sports museum or organ / Monument sports cultural heritage; (3) sports theme park, including a water park, summer pasture, bungee jumping; Hiking commence the journey of exploring the natural; 5. Sports retail stores [9].

Since tourism is a continuous process of, when the tourists gather travel information, and then by the attraction of sports attractions to attract, coupled with the proper service, arrived in Penghu from the sport tourism activities. From the perspective of the leisure experience, the process of engaging in leisure activities, a person's sensory, perception, mind and behavior will continue and the surrounding environment interaction between the feelings and experiences of participants from those interactions. In a participatory process, the interaction between mind and environment, the experience will affect their feelings of value for the travel. With the indivisibility of tourism products, resulting in tourism production and consumption processes occur simultaneously, the tourists must be experienced in order to get a feel for with experience, it is necessary to let the tourists have been satisfied in all respects. The most commonly used by researchers compared to Clawson, Knetsch distinguish between the recreational experience is divided into five stages, respectively, for the plan to the process, live events, return, and memories. Attractions tourists visit each day and engage in different activities, it will have a different experience, and this travel experience feel good or not, will have an impact on follow-up and then travel wishes [10].

Tourism consumption of a product as consumers must pay the price. Although the price is a customer-made product to give up or pay the price, but it is not the customer perceived value "the price paid by the only factor, other non-monetary factors, such as: time costs, search costs, and the spirit of costs should also be included [11]. Perceived value means the consumer to obtain a product or service, the sacrifices, these sacrifices, including money and non-monetary. Monetary means to pay for a product or service, non-monetary aspects of

the product to sacrifice time, or to obtain a product or service in the spirit of giving [12].

Perceived product value means consumers pay in measuring the cost of time, money costs, and purchased the product, the inner self. A subjective experience, but also is worthwhile to the problem. In fact, when the consumer perception of product value, willingness to continue to buy is also higher; relatively low perceived value and its willingness to purchase future will lower. Based on the above discussion, sports tourism attraction, visitors to Penghu tourism experience, have an impact on their perception of the value. Based on the above discussion can be found in the tourists destination for sports tourism attraction in the tourist destination experience for their perceived value to have an impact. Therefore, this study these variables to construct the framework of the study, hoping to understand the impact of tourists choose to Penghu as a sports tourism destination choice behavior, specifically to provide a reference of the marine tourism industry and follow-up study. According to the above background and motivation of this study as well as Penghu tourism, in the purpose of the study can be summarized into the following three points: (A) Analysis of tourists on Penghu sports tourism attraction and tourism experience feelings. (B) Analysis of waters sports tourism attraction and tourism experience. (C) Analysis of waters sports tourism attraction and travel experience for the influence of perceived value.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Subject and Sampling

In this study, the island of Taiwan to Penghu tourism and tourists engage in marine activities, mining point in the way of convenience sampling to investigate. Survey sites paid 600 Jibei sea paradises, Park "Lintou (Aimen beaches) of 600, as well as landscape beach of 600 copies. Survey a total of 1,800 questionnaires, 1620 were recovered, including deduction of to answer not complete or consistent with the questionnaire of 173 total 1447 copies of valid questionnaires.

B. Questionnaire

This research tool is divided into three parts, first part of the sport tourism attractions scale, this section scale department of researchers field trips Penghu water sports features and categories, and then reference Kurtzman and Zauhar the attractions of the sport tourism defined natural (parks, mountains, wilderness) or human (museums, stadiums, shops) [13], and Turco, Riley, and Swart point of view of tourism resources explain sport tourism resource type, and its resources are divided into four: (1) a natural tourism resources; (2) human tourism resources; (3) human tourism resources; (4) local communities prepared [8]. The second part is the travel experience scale, and related waters researchers, and research aspects are environmental point of experience in coastal recreation to explore, including the essence of social, management, and activity facilities, less consideration in psychological and travel arrangements. In this study, in addition to in according to the above classification and

researchers to Penghu tourism of experience, as well as the Penghu area tourist attractions in the understanding of the degree, also refer to relative studies, such as psychological experience, environmental landscape, recreational activities, trip travel arrangements four dimensions. The third part is the "perceived value scale, a total of 3 questions in this part of the scale according to Bolton and Drew study pointed out that consumers perceived value can be divided into money, time, and pay the energy prepared [14]. In the demographic variables of the study demographic variables, including the district of residence, gender, age, marital status, education level, occupation, personal monthly income, tourism experience.

C. Data Analysis

In this study, the valid questionnaires are the use of SPSS For Windows 12.0 version statistical analysis, analysis of the steps include: (1) Used exploratory factor analysis and Cronbach α reliability test of statistical methods to construct the reliability and validity of this research questionnaire. (2) Frequency distribution analysis to Penghu waters sports tourists' demographic variables, sports and tourism attraction, as well as the allocation of travel experience feelings of the situation. (3) Pearson correlation analysis of movement tourist attraction, travel experience, as well as the relationship between the perceived values of each factor. (4) Multiple regression analysis to understand the predictive ability of the visitors in the sport tourism attraction and tourism experience on the perceived value.

D. Reliability and Validity Analysis

After exploratory factor analysis the sport tourism attraction scale of this study extracted three factors were named as "comfortable environment and climate", "water sports and diverse stimulus" and "water activity facilities perfect", the scale cumulative variance of 64.32%. In the travel experience scale, after exploratory factor analysis, to extract four factors, the characteristics of each factor are following options are named as "challenging and fun experience a different cultural experience", "attractions facilities experience" and "goods and services experience", the scale is the cumulative variance of 65.03%. In this study, the perceived value scale only three questions were: 1. spend money is worth it; 2. time spent is worth it; 3. to pay for physical the spirit of participation in the waters activities is worthwhile. This scale is based primarily on the study of Chen and Tsai tourist destination, research the question of perceived value prepared from the study of Chen and Tsai [15], the composition of the reliability of this scale as 84, the average variation of the extracted amount is .76, the scale has good content validity. In terms of reliability, the results of the analysis, the study of sports tourism attraction scale α value of .92; "travel experience" scale α coefficient was .92; the scale of "perceived value" α value of .86. From the above results, show that each scale has a high degree of reliability of this study.

III. RESULTS

A. Demographic Information Analysis

The descriptive statistical analysis of results shows that in these survey valid questionnaires, in terms of gender, male 624, female for 812 people. Mostly in the age to 21-30 years of age, total 736; at least for more than 51 years, a total of 44 people. In marital status, this married 351, unmarried 926. In educational degree, the highest for the universities, namely 809, there is also a Master of 101 people, at least for the Ph.D, namely 19. Occupational, mostly students and a total of 667 people, at least for the freedom of industry, there were 10. In monthly income, the highest NT. \$ 20,000-40,000 total of 414, a minimum of NT.\$ 100,001 or more, 20. The number of trips to Penghu, most people first trips to the total of 571 people, at least for 8 times.

B. Tourist on Sport Tourism in Penghu

The descriptive statistical analysis results show that very high awareness of the sport tourism attraction tourists in Penghu, the average of all items were higher than 4 in 13 attractive items. For good air quality (M = 4.29), followed by a spacious beach (M = 4.27), has a unique landscape, water activities to enjoy the landscape (M = 4.22), ecological resources rich, enterprises water sports and engaging in can enjoy the beautiful eco system (M = 4.21), support the sea sports facilities and equipment for water activities (M = 4.17), the summer climate pleasant, suitable for water activities (M = 4.17), seabed uncontaminated (M = 4.17), clear sea water, suitable for water activities (M = 4.14), sports facilities suitable for water activities (M = 4.12), with a variety of water sports can be engaged in (M = 4.12), with professional coaches, suitable for water activities (M = 4.03), water sports range with distinct security (M = 4.01), with diverse and exciting water activities to meet the risk the demand (M = 4.00).

C. Tourist Travel Experiences in Penghu

The descriptive statistical analysis of results shows that the tourists in Penghu "travel experience" feel good, average of 21 items were above 3.5(mean), which has eight items of the average are higher than 4(mean), in order: Let me taste the delicious specialties and snacks (M = 4.16), exposure to different folk customs and culture (M = 4.11), let my body and feel the release (M = 4.09), water sports give me a high degree of pleasure (M = 4.07), water sports exciting and challenging (M = 4.05), the accommodation made me feel comfortable in the journey (M = 4.05), let me feel a new experience (M = 4.03) as well as water sports facilities safe and perfect (M = 4.01).

D. Correlation Analysis of the Sports Tourism Attraction and Travel Experience

Table I Correlation analysis of the results shows that sport tourism attraction of the three factors (environment, climate, water sports and facilities), the travel experience of three factors (challenge to stimulate different cultural attractions facilities) and the perceived value of each factor has higher relationship exist.

TABLE I
CORRELATION OF THE SPORT TOURISM AND TRAVEL EXPERIENCE

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
A	1							
B	.58*	1						
C	.78*	.68*	1					
D	.58*	.72*	.65*	1				
E	.62*	.55*	.59*	.63*	1			
F	.57*	.52*	.57*	.57*	.65*	1		
G	.38*	.37*	.43*	.42*	.52*	.61*	1	
H	.58*	.48*	.48*	.52*	.72*	.63*	.53*	1

**p<.01

Note: A. comfortable environment and climate,
B. water sports and diverse stimulus
C. water activity facilities perfect
D. challenging and fun experience
E. different cultural experience
F. attractions facilities experience
G. goods and services experience
H. perceived value

E. Regression Analysis of the Sports Tourism Attraction and Travel Experience on the Perceived Value

In this study, the sports tourism attraction, the “comfortable environment and climate”, “water sports and diverse stimulus” and “water activity facilities perfect” the three factors, as well as the travel experience to “challenging and fun experience”, “different cultural experience”, “attractions facilities experience” and “goods and services experience”, the seven factors for predicting variables and the criterion variable “perceived value” factor dimensions, mining forced into the method of regression analysis results, as shown in Table II. Seven predictors, 7 variables were significant level, we can see from the table input and seven variables can predict the feelings of tourists to Penghu tourism value of 32%. Details see the shown in Table II.

TABLE II
REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF THE SPORT TOURISM AND TRAVEL EXPERIENCE ON PERCEIVED VALUE

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	Sig
A	.115	.016	.262	7.232*	.000
B	.071	.029	.073	2.442*	.015
C	.091	.036	.091	2.527*	.012
D	.051	.022	.070	2.317*	.021
E	.088	.015	.171	5.855*	.000
F	.161	.023	.190	7.022*	.000
G	.051	.021	.059	2.356*	.019
R=.562 R ² =.316 adjusted R ² =.312, F=94.85*					

*p<.05

Note: A. comfortable environment and climate,
B. water sports and diverse stimulus
C. water activity facilities perfect
D. challenging and fun experience
E. different cultural experience
F. attractions facilities experience
G. goods and services experience

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Tourist on Sport Tourism

The analysis showed that the awareness of tourists for Penghu sports tourism attraction is very high, obviously attracted to the island of Taiwan tourists to Penghu in marine sport tourism activities, local resources of the natural environment is the main reason. Tourists generally believed that the environmental side, Penghu's marine environment, air quality, spacious beach, has a unique landscape, rich in ecological resources, the summer climate should undersea unpolluted, clear sea water, suitable for water activities. These results also confirmed Ye study the satisfaction of the tourists in Penghu the Jibei waters activities, found that the physical environment of the tourists on coastal recreation activities, the most important for: water quality of contaminated sea water is clear and beautiful natural landscape [16]. The results of Wu [17], Penghu marine sports tourism attraction, also found that “environmental comfort as well as the natural environment” factors, Penghu's marine sports attractive targets, but also to attract tourists to engage in any activity the major attractive.

In addition, this study also found that sports facilities, professional coaches, with diverse and exciting water activities, water sports range with distinct, safe for water activities, but also to attract tourists heading in marine sports tourism activities reasons. The results of the study also confirmed that the sports tourism attraction to attract tourists to visit tourist destinations engaged in sports-related tourism activities, the main reason [18] [19], and with the waters of sightseeing, sports, and recreational activities, to attract people to their destinations engaged in the activities of the main factors [20].

B. Tourist Travel Experiences

Analysis results showed that tourists in Penghu travel experience feel good, especially tourists, that they feel best experience as: “taste the delicious specialties and snacks” as well as “exposure to different folk customs and culture”, “let me feel the release of physical and mental,” “let me feel the new experience” and “accommodation made me feel comfortable”. From the above results, it is clear of tourists to Penghu tourism, have access to physical and mental release, and to experience daily life, culture and sentiments, which is consistent with the purpose of why people leave their own range to travel abroad. The experience of other tourists for Penghu's marine tourism activities feel good, they agree that engaging in water sports provides a high degree of fun, water sports, exciting and challenging and water sports facilities improve safety, also confirmed with the waters related to tourism, sports, and recreational activities to attract people to their destinations in the activities of the main factors [20].

C. Relationship of the Sports Tourism Attraction and Travel Experience

The correlation analysis results show that sport tourism attractions of the three factors (environment, climate, water sports and facilities), the travel experience of three factors (challenge to stimulate different culture, attractions and

facilities) and “perceived value” among the factors have correlated. From the results of the analysis, the tourists to the Penghu feel paid time, spent money, to pay the physical spirit to participate in water sports. Why the worth of reasons feel, mainly related to the Penghu marine sports tourism attraction, and tourists in Penghu's tourism experience. In relative tourism and leisure studies, also found attraction for tourists to experience a significant influence [21], also confirmed in this study. Then this study, the sports tourism attraction of the three factors, as well as the four factors of the tourism experience, a total of seven factors for predicting variables, and the factor of “perceived value” dimensions of the criterion variable, and found that 7 variables have predictive power for the Penghu tourists “perceived value”.

From the above results, the sports tourism attraction indeed to attract tourists to the destinations in the sport tourism activities, the main reason [18][19], but also show that the waters about sightseeing, sports, and recreation activity, it is the main factor to attract people to their destinations to engage in activities [20]. In the travel experience, Gibson pointed out that to understand the experience of sports tourists can help to understand the market segment where, for the local tourism service providers, for experience characteristics of different types of travel products [22]. In addition, this study also confirmed that the “perceived value” is to predict the tourists an important indicator of the intention and behavior [12] [23] [24]. So from the above in terms of visitors to Penghu to engage in marine sport tourism activities, when they think the money spent, time spent, as well as pay for physical spirit to participate in water activities; them in the future will want to come back in Penghu, and be happy to suggest and recommend friends and family travel to Penghu. In addition, to meet the need for improvements at, will be happy to recommend to the competent unit personnel and Penghu as a priority tourism options.

D. Suggestions

Obviously in the waters of sports tourism attraction and travel experience, Penghu water sports, are highly attractive for tourists, is the main reason to attract tourists to Penghu tourism. And tourists in Penghu travel experience, their experience of feeling good, and let them feel the value of tourism. Penghu's tourism industry and government agencies to strengthen the existing attraction and services can help to maintain the live existing tourists. Addition, continuous improvement and enhance the quality of travel may be by the existing tourist and then spread to other visitors, enhance the number of Penghu's tourism.

Attraction in the waters of sport tourism, travel experience on perceived value influences, the results of this study found that “sports tourism attraction of the waters”, “travel experience”, the “perceived value” influential existence. Therefore, the meaning of the dimensions of various factors, the researchers recommended that the Penghu government tourism departments and industry, apart from strengthening the attraction of the publicity Penghu activities, the marine environment clean, ecological conservation, and innovative

activities, must also provide the perfect catering, accommodation, souvenirs beautify the environment clean, attractions, preserve, protect unique cultural assets and tourism services. There are very important to avoid the drive up commodity prices, or to deceive the tourists the case. This allows tourists to leave a good experience in the process of Penghu tourism, and that the time to pay to the Penghu tourism, money, and physical strength is worth it. Follow-up can provide tourists to visit in the wishes of Penghu tourism and recommend to friends and family to become the best marketing channels to promote Penghu tourism.

Subsequent recommendations, this research investigation has actually engage in marine recreational activities in Penghu tourists, so they are attraction for sport tourism in Penghu has actual knowledge, so in this study, the survey before found that their cognitive high. As the researchers can not know whether the subjects is due to Penghu experience before understanding, still yet to come before the Penghu tourism had learned before. It is suggested that future research, conducted similar studies in the future, consider the investigations have not been to Penghu people to understand why the awareness of these subjects Penghu waters sports tourism attraction. They can also investigate why the awareness of the tourists for Penghu's “service quality”, as well as major tourist sources of information.

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